

INFORMAL ECONOMIC ACTIVITIES AND RURAL-URBAN DEVELOPMENT IN CROSS RIVER SOUTH SENATORIAL DISTRICT, NIGERIA

Godfrey Ekene Odinka

&

John Thompson Okpa

Department of Sociology, University of Calabar

Department of Criminology & Security Studies

ABSTRACT

Characterized by unregulated, untaxed, and often undocumented economic activities, the informal sector serves as a major source of livelihood for a large proportion of the population, especially in regions where formal employment opportunities are limited. From street vending, domestic work, informal transport, and small-scale manufacturing to local trading and artisanal services, these activities contribute significantly to household income, job creation, and grassroots economic resilience. In Cross River South, which comprised both coastal urban centers and agrarian rural communities, informal Economic activities bridge the development gap by facilitating local commerce, improving access to goods and services, and fostering micro-enterprises. This study examined the impact of informal Economic activities on rural-urban development in Cross River South Senatorial District, Nigeria. The study specifically explored the relationship between street vending, mobile money operations, local trading and rural-urban development in Cross River South Senatorial District, Nigeria. The study adopted a cross sectional survey design using quantitative, obtained from 400 respondents selected via multi-stage sampling technique. Data were analysed using descriptive statistics and multiple regression in testing the three hypotheses. Results indicate that there is a significant relationship between street vending, mobile money operations, local trading and rural-urban development in Cross River South Senatorial District, Nigeria. Based on the findings, it was concluded that informal Economic activities positively affect rural-urban development in Cross River South Senatorial District, Nigeria. The study recommended among other things that government and financial institutions should develop targeted microfinance initiatives, low-interest loans, and cooperative credit systems tailored to the needs of informal businesses, especially women and youth-led enterprises.

Keywords: Informal Economic Activities, Rural-Urban, Development, Street Vending, Mobile Money Operations, Local trading

INTRODUCTION

Informal economic activities has become an indispensable component of socio-economic life in developing countries. It accounts for a significant proportion of employment and income generation in the African continent. In Nigeria, as in many African states, the informal sector

is not merely a marginal space of survival but a critical driver of livelihoods, especially in the context of weak formal labour markets and limited industrial growth. According to the International Labour Organization (ILO, 2018), the informal sector accounts for more than 80 percent of total employment in Sub-Saharan Africa, underscoring its significance in shaping development trajectories. In rural settings, informal activities such as subsistence farming, petty trading, artisanal work, and small-scale services provide income sources that reduce poverty and drive local consumption. These activities supply agricultural produce and raw materials to urban markets, thereby strengthening rural-urban trade networks. In urban centers, the informal sector absorbs a significant portion of the labour force excluded from the formal sector, particularly youths and women, through activities such as street vending, transport services, tailoring, and small-scale manufacturing. This not only reduces unemployment but also ensures affordable goods and services for urban residents. Moreover, informal activities stimulate migration as rural dwellers move to urban areas in search of economic opportunities, thereby influencing urban growth and the expansion of peri-urban settlements.

Globally, informal economic activities constitutes a significant driver of rural–urban development, particularly in low- and middle-income countries. According to the International Labour Organization (ILO), over 60% of the world’s employed population is engaged in informal employment, with figures rising to 85.8% in Africa and 68.2% in the Asia–Pacific region (ILO, 2018). This sector spans diverse activities, ranging from small-scale farming and artisanal production in rural communities to street vending, domestic work, and micro-enterprises in urban centers. In rapidly urbanizing contexts, the informal sector functions as a major absorber of labour where formal job creation lags. For instance, informal employment accounts for up to 90% of jobs in some Central African countries, 82% in Kenya, and 75% in Tanzania (Kinyanjui, 2019; Chen, 2012). Beyond its economic contributions, informal work often fulfils broader social and developmental roles. A study in Zimbabwe demonstrates that informal actors contribute to urban sustainability through environmental stewardship, recycling, provision of affordable services, and fostering social cohesion in the absence of robust formal structures (Kamete, 2021).

In Asia, informal economies underpin both rural food security and urban service provision. In South Asia, more than 80% of households depend on informal work in agriculture, retail, and transport, with women disproportionately represented in these activities (Meagher, 2016). Similarly, in China, nearly half of urban workers operate in informal employment, helping to bridge gaps in labour absorption and service delivery amid rapid industrial transition (ILO, 2018). Globally, informal economies also provide adaptive, community-centered responses to gaps in formal governance. Informal markets, artisanal networks, and waste recycling initiatives play critical roles in sustaining livelihoods, reducing poverty, and enhancing environmental resilience (Medina, 2020). When integrated into local governance, informal systems can complement formal development strategies by strengthening social safety nets and promoting grassroots innovation.

In Cross River South Senatorial District, Nigeria, informal economic activities such as petty trading, transport services, subsistence agriculture, artisanal production, and small-scale services form the backbone of both rural and urban livelihoods. These activities provide alternative income sources to households, absorb unemployed youth, and act as coping strategies against poverty and economic shocks. They also facilitate rural-urban linkages by

creating markets for agricultural produce, enhancing local commerce, and sustaining urban consumption demands. Thus, informal economic activities not only shape patterns of urbanization and migration but also influence broader processes of rural-urban development in the region. However, despite their significance, informal economic activities remain largely unregulated, poorly documented, and undervalued in development planning (Ikwuyatum, 2016). Government policies often prioritize formal economic structures, neglecting the potentials and challenges inherent in informal activities. This oversight has contributed to persistent poverty, infrastructural deficits, and socio-economic inequalities across rural and urban spaces in Cross River South. Moreover, the informal sector presents ambivalent outcomes: while it fosters employment, resilience, and local development, it is equally associated with precarious working conditions, low productivity, limited access to credit, and lack of social protection. This study examined the impact of informal economic activities on rural-urban development in Cross River South Senatorial District, Nigeria. The study specifically explored the relationship between street vending, mobile money operations, local trading and rural-urban development in Cross River South Senatorial District, Nigeria. Three hypotheses were formulated thus: there is no significant relationship between street vending, mobile money operations, local trading and rural-urban development in Cross River South Senatorial District, Nigeria.

Theoretical framework

The Dual Sector Theory, also known as the Lewis Model of Development, offers a useful framework for understanding the relationship between informal economic activities and rural–urban development. Proposed by Sir W. Arthur Lewis in 1954, the theory explains how economic growth occurs when surplus labour in the rural agricultural sector is transferred to the urban industrial sector where productivity and wages are higher. The underlying proposition is that industrial expansion drives structural transformation by absorbing rural labour and capital, thereby reducing underemployment in the countryside while stimulating urban growth. The theory assumes that the economic is divided into two sectors: the subsistence-based rural agricultural sector with low productivity, and the capitalist-driven urban industrial sector with higher productivity and wages. It also assumes that surplus labour exists in rural areas, meaning that workers can migrate without significantly affecting agricultural output. Furthermore, it holds that industrial profits are reinvested to expand production, creating more employment opportunities, while wages in urban areas remain relatively higher than in rural areas, encouraging migration.

The theory is relevant to this study in the sense that many rural migrants do not secure employment in the formal industrial sector but instead turn to informal work such as street trading, transport services, artisanal labour, and small-scale enterprises. Similarly, in rural areas, informal activities such as subsistence farming, local craftwork, and petty trade provide livelihoods and connect rural populations to urban markets. Thus, the informal economic plays a transitional role, sustaining livelihoods where industrial absorption is limited, and acting as both a bridge and a buffer in the rural–urban development process. Nevertheless, the Dual Sector Theory has been widely criticized for oversimplifying complex realities. It assumes an unlimited supply of surplus labour in rural areas, yet this is not always true given the seasonal nature of agricultural work. It also overlooks the persistence of large informal economies in

urban centers, which contradicts the expectation of a smooth transition into formal industrial employment. Moreover, the assumption of constant wages in the industrial sector does not reflect labour market fluctuations. Critics further argue that the model is overly biased toward industrial growth, downplaying the potential of rural and informal economies to directly drive development. In African contexts like Nigeria, the theory's applicability is also limited by weak infrastructure, poor governance, and institutional constraints that hinder the seamless labour transitions Lewis envisioned.

Methodology

This study adopted a cross sectional survey design to investigate the relationship between informal economic activities and rural–urban development in Cross River South Senatorial District. The design is considered appropriate because it enables the collection of quantitative data from a large population, while also allowing the researcher to identify prevailing patterns, relationships, and implications between informal economic activities and rural–urban development indicators.

The study was conducted in Cross River South Senatorial District, Nigeria, which comprises seven Local Government Areas (LGAs): Akamkpa, Akpabuyo, Bakassi, Biase, Calabar Municipality, Calabar South, and Odukpani. The senatorial district is characterized by diverse socio-economic activities, ranging from fishing, farming, and trading in the rural areas to commerce, transport, small-scale manufacturing, and informal services in the urban centers. This mix of rural and urban settlements makes the area suitable for studying the dynamics of informal Economic activities and their implications for rural–urban development.

The population of the study consists of all individuals engaged in informal economic activities within the senatorial district, including traders, artisans, transport operators, small-scale service providers, subsistence farmers, and market women. A multi-stage sampling technique was employed. In the first stage, four Local Government Areas (two urban and two rural) were purposively selected to capture the rural–urban contrast within the district. The two urban local government areas selected are Calabar Municipality and Calabar south while the two rural local government areas selected were Akpabuyo and Bakassi Local Government Areas. In the second stage, markets, motor parks, and clusters of artisans were identified as key sites of informal activities. Finally, respondents were selected using systematic random sampling, ensuring that participants represented the diversity of informal economic actors in the district. The sample size was a total of 400 respondents selected from the study area. The main instrument of data collection was a structured questionnaire, complimented by key informant interviews (KIIs). Quantitative data collected through questionnaires were coded and analysed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26.0. Descriptive statistics such as frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations were used to summarize data, while inferential statistics such as the regression analysis were employed to test relationships between informal economic activities and rural–urban development.

Result

Of the four hundred questionnaires administered, three hundred and seventy two (372) were retrieved and used for analysis. Results of analysis of demographic data of respondents as presented in Table 1 revealed that; out of the 372 accessible respondents', 146 respondents

representing 39.00% were males, while 226 representing 61.00% were females. As for age distribution of respondents', 104 (28.00) were below 25 years, 211 (57.00) were between 26 – 35 years, 57 (15.00) were between 36 – 45 years. As for religious affiliation, 61 (16.00) practiced Islamic religion, 285 (77.00) practiced Christian religion and 26 (7.00) practiced African Traditional religion. For respondents' educational attainment, 171 (46.00) had primary school education, 103 (28), had secondary school education, while 98 (26.3) had tertiary education. As for respondents' occupation, 104 (28.00) were traders, 197 (53.00) were farmers, 71 (19.00) were mobile money operations. As for how long they had lived in the community; 133 representing (36.00%) had lived in the community for 1-5 years, 111 (30.00) had lived in the community between 6 – 10 years, 70 (19.00) had lived in the community between 11 – 15 years, while 58 respondents' representing 16% had lived in the community for 16-21 years.

Test of hypotheses

Hypothesis one

There is no significant relationship between street vending and rural-urban development in Cross River South Senatorial District, Nigeria. The independent variable in this hypothesis is street vending, while the dependent variable is rural-urban development. Both variables were measured continuously and inferential statistics involving simple linear regression was used to test the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance and the result is presented in Table 1. The result of analysis as presented in table 1, revealed R-value of 0.214a. Correlation coefficient is a standardized measure of an observed degree of relationship between variables, it is a commonly used measure of the size of an effect, and that values of ± 0.1 represent a small effect, ± 0.3 is a medium effect and ± 0.5 is a large effect. Also, the R^2 -value of .047 imply that 47% of total variance is accounted for by predictor variable (street vending). Furthermore, the regression ANOVA revealed that the $F(1, 370) = 10.462$; $p < .05$, is significant. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected. This implies that there is a significant linear association (contribution) of the predictor variable (street vending) on rural-urban development in the study area. The adjusted R^2 (.046) shows some shrinkage of the unadjusted value (.047) indicating that the model could be generalized on the population. Based on the result, it was concluded that there is a significant relationship between street vending and rural-urban development in Cross River South Senatorial District, Nigeria.

TABLE 1

Summary of simple linear regression analysis of the relationship between street vending and rural-urban development

Variables	Mean	Std. Deviation
Street vending	10.7903	4.85744
Rural-urban development	14.3710	5.31710

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Sig
Regression	70.229	1	70.229	10.462	.214a	.047	.046	.001a

Residual	56214.578	370	151.931
Total	56284.806	371	

Source: Field survey, 2024

Hypothesis two

There is no significant relationship between mobile money operations and rural-urban development in Cross River South Senatorial District, Nigeria. The independent variable in this hypothesis is mobile money operations, while the dependent variable is rural-urban development. Both variables were measured continuously and inferential statistics involving simple linear regression was used to test the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance and the result is presented in table 2. The result of analysis as presented in table 2, revealed R-value of 0.230a. Correlation coefficient is a standardized measure of an observed degree of relationship between variables, it is a commonly used measure of the size of an effect, and that values of ± 0.1 represent a small effect, ± 0.3 is a medium effect and ± 0.5 is a large effect. Also, the R^2 -value of .049 imply that 49% of total variance is accounted for by predictor variable (mobile money operations). Furthermore, the regression ANOVA revealed that the $F(1, 370) = 16.441$; $p < .05$, is significant. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected. This implies that there is a significant linear association (contribution) of the predictor variable (mobile money operations) on rural-urban development in Cross River South Senatorial District, Nigeria. The adjusted R^2 (.048) shows some shrinkage of the unadjusted value (.049) indicating that the model could be generalized on the population. Based on the result, it was concluded that there is a significant relationship between mobile money operations and rural-urban development in Cross River South Senatorial District, Nigeria.

TABLE 2

Summary simple linear regression analysis of the relationship between mobile money operations and rural-urban development

Variables	Mean	Std. Deviation
Mobile money	11.9301	3.14650
Rural-urban development	14.3710	5.31710

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Sig
Regression	218.336	1	218.336	16.441	.230a	.049	.048	.001a
Residual	56066.470	370	151.531					
Total	56284.806	371						

Source: Field survey, 2024

Hypothesis three

Local trading has no significant relationship with rural-urban development in Cross River South Senatorial District, Nigeria. The independent variable in this hypothesis is local trading,

while the dependent variable is rural-urban development. Both variables were measured continuously and inferential statistics involving simple linear regression was used to test the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance and the result is presented in table 3. The result of analysis as presented in table 3, revealed R-value of 0.241a. Correlation coefficient is a standardized measure of an observed degree of relationship between variables, it is a commonly used measure of the size of an effect, and that values of ± 0.1 represent a small effect, ± 0.3 is a medium effect and ± 0.5 is a large effect. Also, the R^2 -value of .053 imply that 53% of total variance is accounted for by predictor variable (local trading). Furthermore, the regression ANOVA revealed that the $F(1, 370) = 17.045$; $p < .05$, is significant. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected. This implies that there is a significant linear association of the predictor variable (local trading) and rural-urban development in Cross River South Senatorial District, Nigeria. The adjusted R^2 (.051) shows some shrinkage of the unadjusted value (.053) indicating that the model could be generalized on the population. Based on the result, it was concluded that local trading has a significant relationship with rural-urban development in Cross River South Senatorial District, Nigeria

TABLE 3

Summary simple linear regression analysis of the relationship between local trading and rural-urban development

Variables	Mean	Std. Deviation
Local trading	12.7903	3.71436
Rural-urban development	14.3710	5.31710

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Sig
Regression	6.874	1	6.874	17.045	241a	.053	.051	.001a
Residual	56277.933	70	151.103					
Total	56284.806	371						

Source: Field survey, 2024

Discussion of findings

Street vending and rural-urban development

The findings of this study reveal a significant relationship between street vending as a form of informal economic activity and rural-urban development in Cross River South Senatorial District. Street vending was found to contribute substantially to income generation, employment creation, and the provision of affordable goods and services to both rural and urban populations. This supports previous studies (Bromley, 2000; Chen, 2012) which argue that street vending serves as an important survival strategy for low-income households and a buffer against unemployment in developing economies. The findings also indicate that street vending enhances rural-urban linkages. Rural dwellers bring agricultural produce and locally made

goods to urban centers for vending, while urban-based vendors distribute manufactured goods to rural consumers. In terms of employment, the study established that street vending absorbs a considerable proportion of the labour force that would otherwise remain unemployed. Many participants, particularly women and youth, engage in vending as a primary or supplementary source of livelihood. This corroborates the view that informal sector activities not only sustain households but also enhance local economic resilience (Meagher, 2017). This exchange promotes economic interdependence between rural and urban areas, thereby fostering integrated development. Similar conclusions have been made in global literature, where street vending is recognized as a mechanism through which informal economies bridge rural supply and urban demand (Skinner, 2008). This aligns with findings by Cross and Morales (2007), who contend that while street vending plays a developmental role, its neglect by policy frameworks perpetuates socio-economic marginalization.

Mobile money operations and rural-urban development

The study revealed that mobile money operations have become a transformative force in shaping rural–urban development in Cross River South Senatorial District. Findings indicate that the widespread adoption of mobile money platforms, such as mobile banking applications and agent networks, has significantly enhanced financial inclusion, particularly among rural dwellers who were previously excluded from formal banking systems. This corroborates earlier studies that argue that mobile money reduces barriers to financial access by providing low-cost, flexible, and accessible platforms for savings, transfers, and credit (Aker & Mbiti, 2010; Ouma, Odongo, & Were, 2017). The finding is that mobile money has facilitated rural–urban linkages through remittances. Migrants residing in urban centers are now able to send money to their families in rural areas more conveniently, securely, and at lower transaction costs. This flow of remittances has improved household welfare by enabling investments in education, health, and small-scale enterprises, thereby stimulating local economic growth (Jack & Suri, 2014; Suri & Jack, 2016). Consequently, rural households that were once financially marginalized have gained improved opportunities to participate in development activities.

Moreover, mobile money operations have contributed to poverty reduction and women’s empowerment in rural communities. The findings align with Suri and Jack (2016), who demonstrated that access to mobile money enabled women to move from subsistence farming into small businesses, which enhanced income stability and economic mobility. In the Cross River context, mobile money has provided rural women traders with safer transaction methods, reducing the risks associated with cash handling and improving their ability to reinvest in business activities. The findings also highlight that mobile money operations enhance rural–urban trade integration. Rural farmers and vendors can receive payments instantly from urban buyers, eliminating geographical barriers to commerce. This resonates with Maurer (2012), who argues that mobile money not only facilitates financial transfers but also fosters broader economic transformation by reducing transaction costs and promoting market efficiency.

Local trading and rural-urban development

The findings of the study demonstrate that local trading significantly affect rural–urban development in Cross River South Senatorial District. Local trading, characterized by small-scale commercial activities such as retail shops, open markets, and neighbourhood trading

networks, provides livelihood opportunities for a significant proportion of the population, particularly those excluded from formal employment. This aligns with Meagher (2010), who contends that local trade within the informal Economy is a major source of income and survival strategy for urban and rural households in sub-Saharan Africa. The result revealed that local trading enhances household income and sustains basic welfare, particularly for rural-urban migrants who rely on petty trading as an entry point into urban economic life. Local traders act as intermediaries, connecting rural producers (especially farmers) with urban consumers, thereby creating a supply chain that fosters rural–urban linkages (Tacoli, 2006). This exchange system not only supports food security in urban centers but also ensures that rural producers have reliable access to markets, contributing to local economic development.

The study further shows that local trading strengthens social cohesion by fostering interpersonal networks and community solidarity. Many trading activities are embedded in kinship ties, cultural practices, and informal associations that build trust and collective resilience (Portes & Haller, 2010). This social embeddedness explains why local trading persists despite limited formal support and often serves as a safety net for marginalized groups, particularly women and youth. Additionally, local trading contributes to rural–urban development by stimulating small-scale investments and generating employment. Findings indicate that many households use proceeds from local trading to invest in children’s education, healthcare, and housing, which indirectly promotes human capital development. This is consistent with Chen (2012), who emphasizes that informal trade activities contribute significantly to poverty reduction and inclusive development by redistributing income at the grassroots level.

Conclusion

This study examined the role of informal economic activities (street vending, local trading, and mobile money operations) on rural–urban development in Cross River South Senatorial District. The findings reveal that these economic activities serve as vital sources of livelihood, income generation, and employment for marginalized groups, particularly women and youth, who are often excluded from the formal sector. Beyond their economic contributions, informal activities also facilitate rural–urban linkages by connecting producers and consumers, sustaining household welfare, and fostering social cohesion through interpersonal and community networks. Street vending was found to contribute to food security and access to basic commodities, while mobile money operations enhanced financial inclusion and supported small-scale entrepreneurship. Similarly, local trading acted as a bridge between rural producers and urban markets, stimulating small-scale investments and redistributing income at the grassroots level. Collectively, these informal activities have emerged as indispensable drivers of inclusive development, particularly in contexts where formal economic structures remain weak.

Recommendations

Policymakers should formally recognize informal economic activities as vital contributors to rural–urban development. This recognition should be reflected in development policies that incorporate street vending, local trading, and mobile money operations into urban planning, rural revitalization, and poverty alleviation programmes.

Governments at local and state levels should provide basic infrastructure such as market stalls, storage facilities, sanitation services, and designated vending spaces. These will not only enhance productivity but also reduce conflicts between informal workers and regulatory authorities.

Financial institutions should design inclusive microfinance schemes that cater specifically to informal workers, providing them with affordable loans, savings opportunities, and insurance. This will expand their ability to invest in business growth and contribute more effectively to rural–urban development. Government revenue collection from the informal sector should be fair, transparent, and commensurate with the level of earnings of informal workers. Exploitative levies discourage productivity and undermine developmental contributions.

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